

Event	What we log?
sample UML diagram: refer to the sample UML diagram	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Time <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - if screen is splitted: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - record the period during which the student moves the mouse to the document, scrolls in the UML diagram; this event ends when the student starts to do the next thing (e..g, coding) or moves the mouse away the diagram; - if screen is not splitted <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - record the period during which the student switches to the diagram, views and switches back
do the UML diagram	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Time (the time when the student does the UML diagram)
do the intellij Coding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Time (the time when the student opens the app or starts to code when the app has already been opened)
Chatgpt: consult Chatgpt	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Time (the time when the student types in ChatGpt) - Search: what the student searches
google: search in Google	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Time (the time when the student types in Google) - Search: what the student searches
Stackoverflow: search in Stackoverflow	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Time (the time when the student types in Stackoverflow) - Search: what the student searches
lecture slide: refer to the lecture slide	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Time (the time when lecture slide is opened and the mouse moves to the lecture slide)
Zybook: refer to CS1101 zybook	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Time(the time student opens his/her zybook to check notes and code)
previous PAs: refer to previous programing assignments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Time (the time student opens his/her previous programing assignments to check code and coding styles)
copy & paste code	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Time (the time student copies any specific code) - content: what the student copies and pastes

Post Eval	- Time (the time student opens his/her post-evaluation to answer the questions)
Piazza	- Time (the time student opens Piazza to refer to Piazza Q&As)
Others	other interesting events